

Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} complexes with tyrosine on a dropping mercury electrode.

Experimental

All chemicals used were AnalaR grade. The ligand solution was prepared in double-distilled water. The metals solutions were prepared by dissolving their oxides in minimum amount of hydrochloric acid and were standardised with EDTA⁷. The overall concentrations of potassium chloride, gelatin and rare earth metal ion in the test electrolytic solution were kept constant at 1.0M, 0.01% and 2.0 mM, respectively. The concentration of ligand was varied from 1.0 to 10.0 mM in each case. Ionic strength (μ) was fixed at 1.0, adjusted with potassium chloride. Hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide were used to adjust pH of the test solution at 2.70 ± 0.02 .

Polarograms were recorded on an automatic pen recording polarograph (C.I.C., India), the capillary used had a 'm' value of 2.15 mg s^{-1} and drop time of 3.10 s at 44.0 cm effective height of the mercury ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.15 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$). Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the solution for removing the dissolved oxygen. A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used to measure pH of the solution. All the measurements were made at 25 and 35°, thermostatically controlled.

Results and Discussion

Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} give a well defined three-electron reversible reduction waves at pH 2.70 ± 0.02 in 1.0 M potassium chloride with 0.01% gelatin being used as a maximum suppressor. The difference of $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ was 20 ± 1 mV for Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} and their complexes indicating the reversibility¹¹ of the electrode process. The nature of the waves for metal ions and their complexes was found to be diffusion-controlled as revealed from the straight line plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h}$.

The half-wave potential shifted to more negative value on increasing the concentration of ligand. The method of Lingane¹² was used to determine the formation of 1:1 complexes of Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} with tyrosine. Thermodynamic parameter (ΔG) was calculated from the thermodynamic relations¹³ and given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS (LOG K) AND FREE ENERGY CHANGE (ΔG) OF Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} AND Nd^{III} COMPLEXES WITH TYROSINE

$\mu = 1.0 \text{ KCl}$	log K		ΔG kcal mole ⁻¹	
	25°	35°	25°	35°
Ce^{III}	3.52	3.00	-4.83	-4.25
Pr^{III}	4.35	4.12	-5.96	-5.84
Nd^{III}	4.60	4.35	-6.30	-6.16

The order of stability of complexes was found to be $\text{Ce}^{III} < \text{Pr}^{III} < \text{Nd}^{III}$, which is due to lanthanide contraction⁶.

The gain in the free energies suggest that the complexes are not facilitated at higher temperature⁶.

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Thermal Decomposition of $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$

INDU B. SHARMA*, S. BATRA, SAROJ BALLA
and
R. K. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu,
Jammu-180 001

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A number of hydrates of cerium chloride including the heptahydrate cerium chloride ($\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) are known to exist¹. On heating, cerium chloride is reported to lose water followed by HCl. The present investigation deals with the study of the thermal decomposition of $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, both isothermal and non-isothermal to understand the nature of coordination of water molecules and the identity of the ultimate decomposition product. The final decomposition product has been analysed by X-ray diffractometry.

Experimental

$\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (G.R., E. Merck, 98.5%) was used without further purification. For the isothermal study, a known amount of the compound (500 mg)

was heated at constant temperatures, 393, 413 and 433 K with ± 0.2 K variation in a manually operated thermo-balance and loss in weight was observed. Simultaneous thermal analysis (DTA, TG and DTG) was carried out with a Paulik-Paulik-Erdey MOM derivatograph. The curves were recorded at a heating rate of 10 K/min, while the weight of the sample taken was 100 mg. The identity of the final product was established by X-ray diffraction study.

Results and Discussion

Thermoanalytical studies: The simultaneous DTA-TG-DTG curves of $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at the heating rate of 10 K/min in the static air atmosphere are given in Fig. 1. The thermal changes can be

Fig. 1. Simultaneous DTG-DTA-TG curves of $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at a heating rate of $10^\circ/\text{min}$.

broadly divided into two regions. The first region, lying between 360 and 540 K, comprises of four steps as is evident from the thermogram. In the first step with DTA peak temperature at 398 K and completed at 413 K, the loss in weight from TG (5 mg) corresponds to loss of one water molecule (calculated mass loss for one water molecule is 4.8 mg). The DTA curve shows another broad endothermic peak in the region lying between 443 and 488 K. This broad peak is resolved into two endotherms, which suggests two separate transitions occurring in the region, with peak temperatures at 463 and 473 K. The total weight loss as calculated from the TG curve, corresponding to these temperatures, is 20.5 and 5 mg, showing the loss of four and one water molecules at these steps, respectively. The TG curve emphasises that the first two changes corresponding to the 398 and 463 K peak temperatures do not lead to any stable product formation as the products continue losing weight with change

in temperature while the third step (with peak temperature at 473 K) leads to a stable product over a small region of temperature. The fourth step in this region with the DTA peak temperature at 513 K is associated with 5 mg weight loss corresponding to the loss of another water molecule resulting in the complete dehydration.

In the second DTA region with broad endothermic zone lying between 545 and 730 K, the weight loss as calculated from the TGA is 0 mg which corresponds to the decomposition of the sample to CeO_2 . The d values and their relative intensities as calculated from the room temperature X-ray diffraction studies of the sample drawn at 730 K are given in Table 1. These values when compared with the known values for CeO_2 , show that the product formed is CeO_2 (Ref. 2). The DTA curve of the product exhibits a phase transformation at 825 K without any loss of weight as is evident from the TG and DTG curves. The room temperature X-ray diffraction study of the product of the phase transformation shows that it is again CeO_2 , showing that the process of transformation is reversible.

TABLE 1—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF THE PRODUCT OF THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ AT 730 K AND THE REPORTED DATA FOR CeO_2

Decomposition product		Reported data for CeO_2	
d , Å	Intensity	d , Å	Intensity
3.119	100	3.124	100
2.699	40	2.706	29
1.912	58	1.913	51
1.631	44	1.632	44
1.563	9	1.562	5
1.353	7	1.353	5
1.241	14	1.241	15
1.210	9	1.210	6
		1.104	12
		1.041	9
		0.957	5
		0.915	13
		0.902	7
		0.856	7
		0.825	6
		0.816	5

Isothermal studies: The DTA shows that the first endothermic change is completed at 433 K. To study the mechanism of the process, loss in weight of $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 393, 413 and 433 K at different intervals of time was measured and the results are plotted in Fig. 2. The samples attained constant weight after 60, 45, and 30 min at 393, 413 and 433 K, respectively. The kinetic data obey the Avrami-Erofeev equation^{3,4} in the form, $-\log(1-\alpha) = (kt)^{1/n}$, where α is the fraction of the reaction completed at any time t . Applicability of the equation is shown in Fig. 3, where

Fig. 2. Plots of α (fraction of the reaction completed) vs time t at various temperatures for the isothermal decomposition of $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Fig. 3. Plots of $\log\text{-}\log(1-\alpha)$ vs time t for the isothermal decomposition of $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

$\log\text{-}\log(1-\alpha)$ is plotted vs $\log t$. The energy of activation, as calculated from the Arrhenius plots, comes out to be 14 kcal mol⁻¹. The applicability of the Avrami-Erofeev equation suggests that in these dehydration steps complete random nucleation of the product occurs first, followed by the growth of the nuclei in three dimensions.

Mechanism of dehydration: The specific reaction rate constant values at different temperatures for the various changes in DTA were calculated from the Borchardt and Daniels first order equation⁸,

$$k = \frac{\Delta T}{A - a}$$

where, ΔT is the difference in temperatures between the sample and the reference materials (peak height). A is the total area of the curve and a is the area of

the curve at any temperature T . The energies of activation as calculated from the plots of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ are 36, 59, 55, 55, and 18 kcal mol⁻¹ for the changes corresponding to the peak temperatures of 398, 463, 473, 513 and 683 K, respectively. The energy of activation for the phase transformation process in CeO_2 is 17 kcal mol⁻¹.

The order of the reaction (n) was calculated from the thermogravimetric results by applying the Horowitz-Metzger equation⁶,

$$C_s = (n)^{\frac{1}{1-n}} = \frac{W_s - W_f}{W_o - W_f}$$

where, W_s is the weight of the substance at the peak temperature, W_o is the initial weight and W_f is the final weight of the sample. The values of the order of the reaction for the various changes corresponding to the DTG peak temperature 403, 463, 473, 513 and 683 K are 0.7, 0.5, 0.7, 0.5 and 0.6, respectively. The Coats Redfern equation^{7,8},

$$\log \frac{C^{-1}}{T^2} = \log \frac{2R}{\phi E} \left(1 - \frac{2RT}{E}\right) - \frac{E}{2.303RT}$$

was applied to determine the energy of activation from TGA,

where, $C^{-1} = \log \left(\frac{W_{oc} - W}{W_{oc}} \right)^{-1}$, and W_{oc} = total

mass loss for the particular stage, W = mass loss at temperature T , Z = pre-exponential factor, R = gas constant and ϕ = heating rate in Ks⁻¹. The energies of activation, calculated by plotting $\log C^{-1}/T^2$ vs $1/T$, corresponding to the DTG peak temperatures given above were found to be 30, 38, 90, 61 and 16 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively. The values of the energy of activation as calculated from the TG data when compared with the corresponding values from DTA show fair agreement except for the second and third steps of dehydration. The discrepancy is due to the fact that the two steps lack sharp transition. These transitions are almost continuous, which is substantiated by the TGA, where mass losses for the steps are continuous, and the DTA, where these are part of a broad endothermic region.

The loss of water molecules in different stages suggests that the nature of their bonding is different. The first two stages in which five water molecules are lost exhibit comparatively lower energy of activation. The energies of the activation for the loss of the sixth and seventh molecules are comparatively higher and this suggests that these water molecules are structurally bound. However, the decomposition process, where CeCl_3 decomposes to CeO_2 , exhibits low energy of activation both in the DTA and TGA.

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as yet, although dioxane is a good solvent having a dielectric constant 2.5 at 25°. In the present communication, the conductivity of KCl, KBr, KNO₃, KBrO₃, KIO₃, K₂SO₄, NaCl, NaBr, NaNO₃, NaBrO₃, NaIO₃ and Na₂SO₄ at 10, 20 and 30 wt % of dioxane and at 30, 35, 40 and 45° ± 0.1°, have been studied. The study gives information regarding the ion-solvent interactions from the mobilities and Walden product of the ions in the solvent. Assumption of Stoke⁸ relating Walden product $\Lambda^\circ \eta$, with the radii of the anions has been employed to estimate the single ion mobilities and ionic Walden product.

Conductivity of Electrolytes in Dioxane-Water Mixtures at different Temperatures

P. P. MISRA, N. C. DAS and P. B. DAS*

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College,
Cuttack-753 003

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Experimental

The salts and dioxane used were of E. Merck (extra pure) quality. Preparation of the solvents, solutions and conductance measurements were the same as described earlier³. The conductance measured was accurate up to ± 2 in 1000. The concentration range for uniunivalent salts from 0.01 to 0.001 and for univalent salts from 0.02 to 0.002 mol dm⁻³.

A substantial body of data on the conductances of ions in many aquoorganic solvents, like propylene carbonate, trifluoroethanol, sulpholane, DMSO, DMF and acetone *etc.*¹ have recently been reported. But no study on the conductance of electrolytes in dioxane-water mixtures is reported

Results and Discussion

The Debye-Hückel-Onsager conductance equation is found to be valid as the plot of Λ vs $C^{1/2}$ is linear and the theoretical slope, $(A+B\Lambda^\circ)$ differs from that of the observed one by only 2%. The Λ° values has been obtained from the extra-polated

TABLE 1—IONIC WALDEN PRODUCT ($\Lambda^\circ \eta_0$)/ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ P}$

Temp. °C	Wt % dioxane anion when paired with K ⁺				Anion when paired with Na ⁺					
		10	20	30		10	20	30		
30	Cl ⁻	0.65	0.63	0.63	Cl ⁻	0.63	0.63	0.63		
35		0.63	0.65	0.62		0.61	0.63	0.63		
40		0.66	0.65	0.64		0.63	0.63	0.63		
45		0.66	0.64	0.65		0.61	0.63	0.63		
30		0.60	0.58	0.59		0.57	0.57	0.58		
35	Br ⁻	0.58	0.59	0.58	Br ⁻	0.56	0.56	0.58		
40		0.62	0.61	0.59		0.56	0.58	0.58		
45		0.59	0.59	0.60		0.56	0.55	0.57		
30		0.56	0.53	0.54		0.53	0.53	0.53		
35		0.53	0.56	0.53		0.50	0.53	0.54		
40	NO ₃ ⁻	0.56	0.56	0.54	NO ₃ ⁻	0.52	0.51	0.53		
45		0.55	0.54	0.55		0.52	0.50	0.52		
30		0.47	0.44	0.45		0.42	0.43	0.44		
35		BrO ₃ ⁻	0.45	0.46		0.40	BrO ₃ ⁻	0.43	0.42	0.44
40			0.49	0.49		0.44		0.42	0.44	0.43
45	0.46		0.44	0.45	0.43	0.41		0.42		
30	0.57		0.54	0.55	0.53	0.53		0.54		
35	IO ₃ ⁻		0.55	0.55	0.53	IO ₃ ⁻		0.52	0.53	0.54
40		0.55	0.59	0.55	0.52		0.54	0.54		
45		0.56	0.54	0.55	0.53		0.52	0.53		
30		0.84	0.80	0.67	0.81		0.79	0.66		
35		SO ₄ ²⁻	0.81	0.82	0.78		SO ₄ ²⁻	0.80	0.78	0.66
40	0.83		0.81	0.79	0.79	0.77		0.78		
45	0.83		0.80	0.80	0.80	0.77		0.78		
30	0.70		0.71	0.70	0.62	0.61		0.60		
35	K ⁺		0.71	0.69	0.70	Na ⁺		0.63	0.62	0.60
40		0.69	0.69	0.70	0.62		0.61	0.60		
45		0.70	0.71	0.69	0.62		0.61	0.61		

*present address: Director, State Forensic Science Laboratory, Rasulgarh, Bhubaneswar-751 010.